

The simplified reaction takes place as given below :

Experimental

All chemicals of standard quality were used. All liquids were freshly distilled.

A solution of phenol (4.7 g) and NaOH (2.1 g; 5 per cent excess of mol/mol of phenol) in water was made upto 125 ml. To it freshly distilled dimethyl sulphate (10 ml) and the specified quantity of the catalyst (dissolved and made upto 125 ml in chloroform) were added. The reaction mixture was stirred and aliquots (10 ml) at 15 min intervals were withdrawn without disturbing the stirring. After each withdrawal 5 ml of chloroform and 5 ml of water were added to the reaction mixture to make up the volume. The sample was partially evaporated to drive away the solvent and diluted to 47 ml with water. From it 10 ml were taken and diluted to 50 ml with water, then from the latter 1.5 ml aliquot was taken and diluted to 10 ml with 4% NaOH. 1 ml of the alkaline solution was mixed with buffer solution (16 ml; pH 9.2), a 0.3% 4-aminoantipyrine solution (1 ml) and a 1% potassium ferricyanide solution (2 ml); pH of the solution was 9.2. Phenol in different aliquots was estimated³

Studies in Phase Transfer Catalysis. Part-II. Methylation of Phenol

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McKILLOP *et al.*¹ reported the preparation of a variety of phenolic ethers under phase transfer catalytic conditions. We have conducted a study on methylation of phenol by dimethyl sulphate at room temperature with a view to assess the catalytic activity of several quaternary ammonium compounds.

TABLE I—PERCENTAGE CONVERSION DATA

Sl. no.	Catalyst	Solvent chloroform								Solvent benzene							
		NaOH 1 mol mol ⁻¹				NaOH 2 mol mol ⁻¹				NaOH 1 mol mol ⁻¹				NaOH 2 mol mol ⁻¹			
		Time (min)				Time (min)				Time (min)				Time (min)			
1.	Nil	53	65	73	73	79	85	85	85	85	88	90	90	88	95	95	95
2.	Tetrabutylammonium bromide, 5 mmol mol ⁻¹	69	76	80	80	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
3.	Tetrabutylammonium bromide, 10 mmol mol ⁻¹ and above	77	82	82	82	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
4.	Tricaprylmethyl ammonium chloride, 5 mmol mol ⁻¹ and above	80	87	87	87	100	100	100	100	88	95	95	95	100	100	100	100
5.	Cetyl trimethylammonium bromide, 5 mmol mol ⁻¹ and above	75	80	80	80	88	90	90	90	90	95	95	95	100	100	100	100
6.	Benzyl dimethyl hexadecylammonium chloride, 5 mmol mol ⁻¹ and above	58	65	74	75	85	87	87	87	90	94	94	94	95	100	100	100
7.	Triethyl benzylammonium chloride, 5 mmol mol ⁻¹ and above	88	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	90	95	95	95	100	100	100	100

in a Systronics spectrophotometer at 510 nm and the conversion was determined. The final solution contains 6 mcg/ml of the phenol.

Different catalyst concentrations were employed. Since the conversions in all cases reached maximum with 10 mmol mol⁻¹, two catalyst concentrations, namely 5 and 10 mmol mol⁻¹ of phenol were selected. Two concentrations of sodium hydroxide (1 and 2 mol/mol of phenol) were employed because these were found to be sufficient to demonstrate the effect of alkali concentration on conversion. Two solvents chloroform and benzene were employed. Benzene (Merck) was repurified by stirring with concentrated sulphuric acid, then washed, dried over fused calcium chloride and distilled. The purification was necessary since the traces of impurities were found to interfere with the spectrophotometric determination of phenol. The salient results are presented in Table 1.

Catalytic activity was found to be quite significant in improving the conversion by 5–20%. All the catalysts employed functioned almost equally. Benzene was found to be a better solvent than chloroform.

References

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3. R. J. LOCOSTE, S. H. VENABLE and J. C. STONE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, **31**, 1246.